

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF AUTOMATED SOLUTIONS IN IMPROVING PENSION BENEFIT CALCULATIONS AND PENSION ASSET MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the role of automated solutions in optimizing pension systems (PS) aimed at calculating pension benefits (PB) and managing pension assets (PA). The modern challenges faced by PS, including demographic changes and growing demands for financial resources, are analyzed. The use of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, and robo-advisors for automating processes, enhancing calculation accuracy, minimizing errors, and improving asset management is examined. The impact of automated solutions on increasing pension fund returns and reducing risks is analyzed. Examples of successful applications of automated systems are provided, demonstrating their significant superiority over traditional methods of managing PB.

Keywords: automated solutions, pension benefits (PB), pension assets (PA), artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, robo-advisors, pension systems (PS).

Introduction

Pension systems (PS) play a crucial role in maintaining social stability and economic security for citizens in the post-employment period. However, with the increasing number of retirees and the growing complexity of pension fund structures, significant challenges in managing pension benefits (PB) and assets arise. These challenges include difficulties in accurately calculating benefits, managing pension assets (PA) in changing market conditions, and ensuring data transparency and security. Traditional data processing and PA management methods are becoming less effective and prone to errors, highlighting the need for modernization and automation of these processes.

Automated solutions based on modern technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, and algorithmic asset management offer new opportunities for improving PS functionality. These technologies not only accelerate calculations and minimize errors but also provide a personalized approach to PA management, enhancing returns and reducing risks. The goal of this research analyzes the role of automated solutions in improving PB calculations and PA management.

Main part. Challenges in the PB system

The PB system is an essential element of the social policy of most countries, providing financial support to citizens after retirement. It consists of numerous mechanisms and processes aimed at collecting and managing PA, as well as calculating and paying pensions. The sustainability and efficiency of such a system largely determine the quality of life for the elderly population, as well as the level of social and economic stability.

Currently, PS worldwide are facing a number of significant challenges related to demographic changes and the growing demands on pension funds. These challenges require not only a revision of current approaches to PA management but also the implementation of more accurate and efficient solutions, including automated ones.

One of the main challenges is the demographic transformation observed in most developed countries. As the population ages, the proportion of people of retirement age increases, while the working-age population, which funds PS, decreases. This imbalance creates additional pressure on PS, requiring increased funding for PB. In 2022, about 17,3% of the U.S. population was over 65 years old. This is higher than in recent years, and it is expected that by 2050 this figure will reach 22% (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Share of the elderly population (65 and older) in the total population of the U.S. [1]

As the number of retirees increases, the volume of payments rises, placing additional financial strain on PS. In traditional systems, calculations are often performed manually or using outdated methods, which slows down data processing and increases the risk of errors. Errors caused by human intervention can range from simple calculation mistakes to complex errors in planning and forecasting. These mistakes not only create risks for pension funds but also undermine public trust in PS. The automation of management and calculation processes offers a solution that minimizes human error, enhances operational accuracy, and provides more reliable asset management.

Tools of automated systems in PB calculations

The automation of PB calculations and PA management has become an integral part of modern PS. The introduction of technologies such as AI, blockchain, and machine learning algorithms significantly increases the efficiency of these processes.

AI-based systems enable the automation of complex PB calculations, predicting future needs of pension funds, and analyzing large volumes of data. **Machine learning**, a subset of AI, helps PS adapt to changing conditions and demographic shifts by using historical data to improve forecasts and adjust payments. These systems can analyze behavioral and market data to better manage assets and minimize risks.

Blockchain technologies provide transparency and security of data within the PB system. Due to the decentralized nature of blockchain, data on pension contributions and payments are protected from unauthorized alterations, eliminating the possibility of fraud and errors in transfers and calculations. **Algorithmic asset management systems, or robo-advisors**, are used to automate investment decisions in pension funds [2]. These systems analyze data in real-time, adjust asset management strategies, and allocate funds across various asset classes to maximize returns and minimize risks.

One of the important tasks of automation in PB calculations is **accelerating the processing of large**

volumes of data and minimizing human error. Automation can virtually eliminate mistakes related to manual data entry and calculations. For instance, blockchain-based systems ensure full transparency and reliability of data, making them immune to errors caused by human intervention. This not only improves payment accuracy but also enhances public trust in PS. Automated systems can instantly process PB calculation requests, reducing processing time from weeks or days to seconds. This is particularly important in situations where quick adjustments to calculations are needed due to changes in legislation, economic conditions, or individual circumstances.

Automated systems also significantly improve the **accuracy of PB forecasting.** AI-based systems can predict future needs of pension funds, taking into account the dynamics of the retiree population and accumulated funds. This allows funds to plan their asset management strategies in advance and adjust contribution levels. Automated systems can also consider individual characteristics of each retiree, such as work history, age, income level, and medical needs, to accurately calculate the size and timing of payments [3]. This not only enhances fairness in pension distribution but also prevents problems related to overspending or underfunding.

Robo-advisors and algorithmic asset **management systems use predictive models to optimally allocate funds across investment instruments.** This significantly increases pension fund returns and minimizes potential losses by flexibly adapting to market conditions.

A successful example of PB automation is the implementation of automated systems in the **social security administration.** It uses digital algorithms for pension calculations, automatic data updates, and predictive analysis, which shortens request processing times and improves payment accuracy [4].

Thus, the automation of PB calculation processes and asset management creates a foundation for more accurate, transparent, and efficient PS, ensuring the

sustainability of pension funds and improving the quality of service for citizens.

Automated PA management

The automation of PA management using technologies such as robo-advisors has significantly changed the approach to investments and pension fund management. These solutions contribute to more efficient asset allocation, risk minimization, and lower operational costs, ultimately increasing pension fund returns and stability. Robo-advisors are automated systems that use algorithms to manage assets based on specified parameters such as risk level, investment goals, and time horizons. In the context of pension fund management, these systems handle asset allocation, risk assessment, and yield optimization functions.

One of the aspects of the work of algorithmic consultants is the **collection and analysis of data for effective asset allocation**. They use historical data, market trends, and macroeconomic indicators to offer optimal investment solutions. Automated asset management plays an important role in **reducing human error and lowering the operational costs of pension funds**. Algorithmic management minimizes the likelihood of subjective decisions and allows operations to be based on strict mathematical models [5]. Automation also reduces administrative costs related to reporting, data processing, and monitoring the execution of transactions. Ultimately, this creates a more transparent and efficient PA management system, ensuring the long-term stability of funds.

Robo-advisors **process data in real-time**, allowing for prompt responses to market changes and portfolio adjustments according to current conditions. Based on contributors' income, age, planned retirement, and other characteristics, algorithms can offer individualized asset management solutions. Data is used to balance portfolios across asset classes, minimizing risks and increasing returns. For pension funds, this means that assets are allocated not only based on current yields but also on long-term forecasts, making management more resilient to economic shocks.

An example of successful implementation of automated PA management systems is the experience of companies such as **Betterment and Wealthfront**. They are among the leaders in automated asset management, including pension savings, using algorithms to create balanced portfolios that consider clients' risk levels and investment goals. According to reports, Betterment and Wealthfront robo-advisors have consistently achieved high returns for pension funds by using passive management principles with broad asset diversification, which helps reduce risks in volatile markets [6].

Automation of PA management through algorithmic systems provides pension funds with effective tools for improving investment strategies, reducing risks, and increasing returns. The introduction of automated solutions in PB calculation and PA management systems has demonstrated significant superiority of these technologies over traditional methods (table 1).

Table 1.

Comparative analysis of traditional and automated solutions in PB [7, 8]

Aspect	Traditional systems	Automated systems
Accuracy of calculations	Dependence on manual calculations, increased risk of errors.	High accuracy through the use of algorithms and automation.
Processing speed	Slow data processing, delays in calculations.	Fast processing of data and calculations in real time.
Management costs	High labor and administration costs.	Reducing operating costs through automation.
Risk of errors	Common mistakes related to the human factor.	Minimal risk of errors due to the exclusion of the human factor.
Flexibility to adapt to changes	Limited ability to adapt in the short term.	High flexibility and ability to respond quickly to changes.
Monitoring and risk management	It requires the participation of specialists, it is difficult to control risks in real time.	Automatic risk monitoring and real-time strategy correction.
Transparency for users	Limited user access to PA information	Full user access to their data through online platforms

According to the author, automated systems provide significant improvements in managing PB and assets, particularly in areas such as calculation accuracy, risk monitoring, and adaptive flexibility. By eliminating the human factor and utilizing algorithms, automation minimizes errors and enhances performance. While traditional systems continue to be used in certain cases, they are becoming increasingly inefficient in the face of growing complexity in financial operations and the demands of managing pension funds.

Conclusion

Automated solutions play a crucial role in modernizing PS, significantly improving PB calculations

and PA management. The implementation of technologies such as AI, algorithmic asset management, and blockchain not only enhances the accuracy and speed of calculations but also minimizes errors related to human intervention. Software solutions enable real-time asset allocation, data transparency for users, as well as flexibility and adaptability to changing economic conditions.

Furthermore, the automation of PA management improves risk management and increases fund returns. Automated monitoring systems and algorithms allow for effective management of market, credit, and operational risks, which is particularly important in the un-

certainty of global financial markets. Successful examples of automated systems implementation in various countries demonstrate that such solutions can increase the resilience of pension funds and ensure stable payments in the long term. Thus, the automation of processes in PS is not just a step toward increasing efficiency but also an important factor in ensuring the reliability and sustainability of PB in the face of growing demographic and economic challenges.

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